

SLOVENIAN OPEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY

A Cooperative Approach for Common Benefits

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VISION

In order to achieve better research results and international competitiveness, the proposal of the new Slovenian Research and Innovation Strategy envisions the establishment of a national open science community as an integrated, cooperative open science ecosystem of all Slovenian key stakeholders, including infrastructures, research libraries, and other participants in public and private services in the field of open science:

- A comprehensive and transparent open science ecosystem that will operate in a complementary way in the field of services, infrastructures, and training to improve the working conditions of researchers, encourage the dissemination, exchange, and reuse of knowledge through open access, develop open science-related skills, and set up a training system for target users.
- Representation of national interests in the European Open Science Cloud.

LEGISLATION

- Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act of the Republic of Slovenia
- Research and Innovation Strategy of Slovenia (RISS) 2021-2030 (measure: establishment of national OS community)
- Regulation on the implementation of scientific research work in accordance with the principles of Open Science (in preparation)
- university libraries to become focal points of OA and RDM support activities for public universities and broader (upcoming project of the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport)

OS COMMUNITY STAKEHOLDERS

- infrastructure (NREN, NGI)
- ERICs and e-infrastructures, national nodes
 - RDA, OpenAIRE, CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS, RESILIENCE, E-RIHS, ...
- research performing organizations
- libraries & academic presses
- data management performing organizations (archives support)
- funders and policy makers

COMMON GROUND

- national bibliographic system and services COBISS, connected with institutional repositories (national in-house software) which are upgraded in terms of Open Access demands
- national open access infrastructure (OAI)
- national academic and research network
- national grid infrastructure
- OS community as the national network of OS stakeholders

LIBRARY/DATA ARCHIVE AS THE DRIVER

- facilitator of the Open Science Community – National Open Science Cloud Initiative
- connecting stakeholders network
- support to on-boarding of Slovenian knowledge to the European Open Science Cloud
- EOSC promoter
- training and service provider
- sharing, preserving and curating knowledge through quality data and metadata

SERVICE CATALOGUE

- marketplace of Slovenian knowledge
- common entry point to e- and research infrastructures, high-performance resources, data & publication management tools
- training for service providers and end-users
- boost interdisciplinary collaboration
- connections between different levels of stakeholders

COMING SOON:
SLOVENIAN OPEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY PORTAL: national single entry point for common collaboration on open science progress

University of Maribor Library

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SLOVENIAN
OPEN SCIENCE
COMMUNITY

National Initiatives for Open Science in Europe